

Original Article

LEVERAGING DIGITAL SKILLS FOR EMPLOYEE WORKPLACE OPERATIONAL EFFICIENCY IN POLYTECHNICS IN NASARAWA STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

The study investigated the leveraging on digital skills for employee workplace operational efficiency in Polytechnics in Nasarawa State, Nigeria. Three research questions were answered while three null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The population of the study was 681 non-teaching staff of Federal Polytechnic, Nasarawa Toto and Isa Mustapha Agwai I Polytechnic, Lafia both in Nasarawa State. Through purposive sampling technique, 266 ICT-related non-teaching staff across the two Polytechnics comprising (146 males and 120 females) were sampled as respondents. The instrument for data collection was a 25-item structured questionnaire. The instrument was validated by three Business Education experts while the reliability of the instrument was ascertained using Cronbach Alpha reliability technique which yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.941. Data extracted from the 266 retrieved copies of the questionnaire were analyzed using mean, standard deviation and t-test statistics. From the data collected and analyzed, the study found that digital skills possessed by employees in Polytechnics in Nasarawa State are low. From the findings, the study among others recommended that digital technologies and periodic organization of conferences, workshops, seminars, and symposium by the management of the institutions should be organized for their improved operational efficiency.

Keywords: *Digital skills, employee, operational efficiency and Polytechnics*

Introduction

All over the world, the workplace is changing as a result of digitization, automation and modernization which Nigeria is not an exception. In the face of rapid digital reformation, acquiring digital skills has become a pressing imperative for Polytechnics and other tertiary institutions in Nigeria. Polytechnic education equips students with the technical expertise and vocational skills required to excel in

The modern workforce, fostering opportunities for productive employment and sustainable livelihoods. As a vital source of skilled technicians and technical Personnel, polytechnics play a crucial role in driving economic growth (Chedi, 2015). As technology continues to reshape the economy, the demand for a digitally skilled workforce in polytechnics has become increasingly urgent, necessitating a paradigm shift in the workplace. Developing these skills is crucial not only for individual professional

advancement but also for driving business success and maintaining a competitive edge. By investing in digital skills training, organizations can significantly boost their operational efficiency and thrive in a technology-driven world. Digital skills encompass the proficiency to leverage digital tools, technologies, and platforms to achieve optimal outcomes. The acquisition of these skills is crucial across diverse sectors, particularly in polytechnics, where they significantly enhance operational efficiency, boost productivity, and elevate overall performance (Sartika, Astuti, Chasanah & Riyanto 2023). By automating routine tasks, employees can focus on higher-value work, leading to increased confidence and productivity (Adam, 2022). Digital skills also involve the capacity to effectively locate, assess, utilize, share, and generate digital content using various devices, including computers, smart phones, and other digital technologies (UNESCO 2018, Okeji, Nwankwo, Anene & Olorunfemi 2020). Similarly, Kirikoi (2015), stated that digital skills pertain to the use of technological tools in the workplace for managing information, including recording, storing, processing, retrieving, transferring, and disseminating data. Examples of such tools include computer systems, lap tops and communication devices. Furthermore, digital technologies encompass methods, tools, and infrastructure that electronically generate, manage, and analyze data. They are diverse and include: computers, internet, multimedia, mobile phones, software technologies, servers, and websites among others (Okolocha & Nwaukwa 2020) In essence, digital skills enable individuals to critically engage with digital information, harness its potential, and thrive in an increasingly digital world (Triparty 2019, UNESCO 2018). In agreement, Berger and Frey (2018) stated that majority of occupations now require application of digital skills as they have become critically important for present and future

jobs. To be relevant, polytechnic employees need to acquire new sets of skills like computer literacy, online navigation, e-mail, data entry, digital communication as well as basic software applications Adams (2022). This is so because studies carried out by Helsper and Reidorf (2016) have revealed that public and private organizations worldwide are embarking on digitalization of their services which is becoming a risk on the general public becoming digitally excluded. The danger of becoming digitally excluded poses a threat to all individuals who do not have the necessary skills to handle the digitalization of the various services of life domains. Also, research carried out by experts in the field of digital skills like Deursen & Van (2014) stressed that digital skills and competences, and the ability to make use of digital media in autonomous and strategic way are of increasing importance to ensure full participation in the digital work environment by users. Workers are expected to acquire computational procedures that are required everywhere to manage job tasks. The ability to solve problems with digital technologies is linked to the achievement of work-related goals, which rely on digital technologies (Griffin & Care 2015). The 21st-century skills are essential competencies that office administrators must acquire to thrive in the information age (Junior, Macada, Brinkhues & Montesdioca (2014). The digital revolution is an unstoppable force, transforming the landscape with its four key attributes: decentralization, globalization, harmonization, and empowerment. As digitalization advances, it is giving rise to innovative tools that foster greater autonomy, flexibility, and freedom. This shift is increasingly requiring individuals to develop an entrepreneurial mindset, think creatively, and possess excellent self-management skills (Khan & Pirzada 2013, Okolie & Ogbaekirigwe 2014, Olaopa, 2015). In today's digital landscape, polytechnic sector workers need to

acquire digital skills to enhance work efficiency and productivity. Digital skills can be developed through self-directed learning, formal education, and on-the-job training, encompassing foundational concepts, technical proficiency, and problem-solving abilities. The impact of digital skills technologies is profound, transforming the way people live and work. Digitally literate employees are empowered to identify and address operational inefficiencies, leveraging their technical expertise to optimize work processes and drive revenue growth. Developing robust digital literacy skills enables non-teaching staff to navigate workplace transformations and harness emerging technologies essential for their roles. Moreover, employers also reap significant benefits from having a digitally literate workforce, including enhanced productivity, improved innovation, and increased competitiveness. (Ahmad, Lazim, Shamsuddin, Wahab & Seman 2019). As the digital economy expands and new technologies continue to emerge, the demand for digital skills is expected to skyrocket (Anita 2024). This accelerating trend underscores the urgent need for individuals, organizations, and institutions to prioritize digital literacy and upskilling, ensuring they remain competitive and relevant in an increasingly digital landscape. Digital technologies have democratized access to information, facilitated collaboration, and optimized processes, making digital skills an essential component of organizational success (Nadeau & Landau, 2018). As a result, adapting to and developing digital skills is crucial for individuals to remain relevant and effective in the modern workforce. The rapid advancement of technology has significantly altered business processes, practices, and the role of employees in polytechnics. The modern office environment is complex and challenging, with the proliferation of office technologies and information systems transforming traditional methods. As a result, employees face

numerous challenges in adapting to new technologies, exacerbated by the pressures of globalization and the changing nature of work. Chedi (2015) and (Olofin et al 2015) noted that Non-teaching staff in higher institutions face challenges in adopting digital skills due to factors such as lack of basic computer skills, inadequate ICT infrastructure, insufficient training and technical support, cost of internet data and services, as well as age, gender, and attitude towards technology. Also, Oyebisi & Oyelami (2020) observed that Polytechnic staff often struggle to leverage technology effectively due to inadequate digital skills, exacerbated by limited training programs and professional development opportunities. This hindrance to staff growth and productivity is further compounded by outdated equipment and poor maintenance, creating an unfavorable work environment. Moreover, dissatisfaction with compensation, lack of recognition, and limited career advancement prospects can erode staff morale and motivation, ultimately impacting overall performance. The accelerating pace of technological change has created a substantial skills gap among polytechnic employees, hindering their ability to adapt to emerging digital tools and platforms. This, in turn, impacts workplace operations and overall institutional performance. Employers are concerned that workers lack the necessary digital skills to effectively perform their job tasks, leading to decreased operational efficiency.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study is to ascertain the Digital Skill for Employee Workplace Operational Efficiency in Polytechnics in Nasarawa State. Specifically, the study determined:

- (i) The digital skills possessed by employees in Polytechnics in Nasarawa State?
- (ii) The extent digital technology is available among polytechnics' employees in Nasarawa State?

(iii) The effect of digital skills on employee workplace operational efficiency in polytechnics in Nasarawa State?

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

(i) What are the digital skills possessed by employees in Polytechnics in Nasarawa State?

(ii) To What extent is digital technology available among polytechnic employees in Nasarawa State?

(iii) What is the effect of digital skills on employee workplace operational efficiency in polytechnics in Nasarawa State?

Research hypotheses

The following null hypotheses have been formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

H0₁: There is no significant difference between the mean rating of male and female employees on the digital skills possessed in polytechnics in Nasarawa State.

H0₂: There is no significant difference between the mean rating of male and female employees on the extent of availability of digital technology in polytechnics in Nasarawa State.

H0₃: There is no significant difference between the mean rating of male and female employees on the effect of digital skills on employee in polytechnic work place operational efficiency in Nasarawa State.

Methodology

The study was carried out in Federal Polytechnic and Isa Mustapha Agwai Polytechnic, Lafia both in Nasarawa State. Three research questions were answered while three null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study was carried out using descriptive survey research design. Descriptive survey research design according to Shona (2022) is a research method that aims at accurately and systematically describes a population, situation or phenomenon through data collected with the use of questionnaire. Descriptive survey design is suitable

for this study because copies of well-structured questionnaire were administered to collect data from the respondents the population of the study was 681 non-teaching staff of the two Polytechnics. Simple random sampling technique was used to carefully select 266 ICT-related non-teaching staff across the two Polytechnics comprising (146 males and 120 females). The instrument for data collection was a 25-item questionnaire structured into three major sections in line with the three specific purposes of the study. Section one was structured to obtain data on digital skills possessed by the non-teaching staff in the Polytechnics. Section two of the questionnaire was made to gather data on the extent to which digital technologies is available among the Polytechnic employees while section three was made to obtain data on effect of digital skills on employees workplace operational efficiency in Polytechnics in Nasarawa State. The response options of the questionnaire for sections one and three were 4-point rating scale of: Strongly Agreed (SA) = 4, Agreed (A) = 3, Disagreed (D) = 2 and Strongly Disagreed (SD) = 1. On the other hand, the response options for section two of the questionnaire were 4-point rating scale of: Very High Extent (VHE) = 4, High Extent (HE) = 3, Low Extent (LE) = 2 and Very Low Extent (VLE) = 1. The instrument was validated by three Business Education experts while comments of the experts were used to improve the quality of the final draft of the instrument for quality data collection. The reliability of the instrument was ascertained by trial testing 15 copies of the instrument on 15 ICT-related non-teaching staff of Plateau State Polytechnic, Barkin Ladin, and Plateau State. Data collected from the trial testing were analyzed using Cronbach Alpha reliability technique which yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.941. Data were collected by the researcher with the help of research assistants. Due to strict follow up, the 266 copies of the questionnaire administered to the respondents in the

two Polytechnics were duly filled and retrieved representing 100% rate of return. Data extracted from the 266 retrieved copies of the questionnaire were analyzed using mean, standard deviation and t-test statistics. In taking decision on the research questions, cut-off point of 2.50 was used on 4-point rating scale. Based on the obtained cut-off point value, any item with mean value of 2.50 and above was interpreted as “Agreed” while items with mean values less than 2.50 were interpreted as “Disagreed” also, any item with mean value of 2.50 and above was interpreted as “high extent” while items with mean values less than 2.50 were interpreted as “low

extent”. The hypothesis of no significant difference was accepted when the t-calculated (t-cal) value was less than the t-critical (t-tab) value of 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance while hypothesis of no significant difference was to be rejected when the t-calculated (t-cal) value was greater than the t-critical (t-tab) value of 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

Research Question One

What are the digital skills possessed by employees in Polytechnics in Nasarawa State?

The data for answering research question one are presented in Table 1 below.

Table 1: Mean Ratings of the Responses of Respondents on Digital Skills Possessed by Employees in Polytechnics in Nasarawa State (n = 266)

SN	Digital skills possessed by employees	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	SD	Rmks
1.	Navigate online	40	50	121	55	2.28	0.95	Disagree
2.	Use digital communication devices	45	61	88	72	2.29	1.04	Disagree
3.	Manage digital information	89	80	65	32	2.84	1.02	Agree
4.	Access Digital content	94	70	40	62	2.73	1.17	Agree
5.	Software application	21	33	189	23	2.19	0.70	Disagree
6.	Apply computational procedure	52	50	58	106	2.18	1.15	Disagree
7.	Use computer storage devices	60	78	66	62	2.51	1.08	Agree
8.	Use the computer to generate management reports	11	21	186	48	1.98	0.65	Disagree
9.	Make use of e-mail to send documents	23	39	107	97	1.95	0.92	Disagree
10.	Access Google	170	21	60	15	3.30	1.07	Agree
	Cluster Summary	-	-	-	-	2.43	0.89	Disagree

Note: \bar{X} = Mean; SD = Standard Deviation; N = No of Respondents; N = 266.

The result in Table 1 revealed that the mean values of the respondents on items 3, 4, 7, and 10 are 2.84, 2.73, 2.51 and 3.30 respectively which are all greater than the cut-off point value of 2.50 on 4-point rating scale. This indicates that the respondents agreed that the four identified items are the digital skills possessed by employees in Polytechnics in Nasarawa State. On the other hand, the mean values on items 1, 2, 5, 6, 8 and 9 are 2.28, 2.29, 2.19, 2.18, 1.98 and 1.95 respectively which are in each case less than the

cut-off point value of 2.50 on 4-point rating scale. This implies that the respondents disagreed that the six remaining items are digital skills possessed by employees in Polytechnics in Nasarawa State. The overall cluster mean value of 2.43 was less than 2.50 cut-off point, indicating that the respondents disagree that, employees in Polytechnics in Nasarawa State possessed digital skills. The standard deviation values of the 10 items in the table ranged from 0.65 - 1.17 which suggests that the responses of the respondents were close to one another and the mean.

Hypothesis One

There is no significant difference in the mean rating of male and female employees on the digital skills possessed in polytechnics in Nasarawa State.

The data for testing hypothesis one is presented in Table 2 below.

Table 2: Result of t-test Statistics of no Significant Difference in Mean Ratings of Male and Female Employees on the Digital Skills Possessed in Polytechnics in Nasarawa State.

Variables	N	\bar{X}	SD	DF	Std. Error	t-cal	t-tab	Level of sig.	Rmks
Male employees	146	2.42	0.93						
				264	0.077	0.17	1.96	0.05	NS
Female employees	120	2.4	0.83						

Note: NS = Not Significant at 0.05.

The data presented on the t-test statistics in Table 2 showed that the t-calculated (t-cal) value of 0.17 was less than the t-table (t-tab) value of 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance and 264 degree of freedom. This indicated that there was no significant ($p < 0.05$) difference in the mean ratings of the responses of male and female employees on the digital skills possessed in polytechnics in Nasarawa State. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant

($p < 0.05$) difference in the mean ratings of the responses of male and female employees is accepted on hypothesis one.

Research Question Two

To what extent is digital technology available among polytechnics' employees in Nasarawa State?

The data for answering research question two are presented in Table 3 below.

Table 3: Mean Ratings of the Respondents on the Extent to which Digital Technologies are available among Polytechnics Employees in Nasarawa State (n = 266)

SN	Extent of digital technologies available	VHE	HE	LE	VLE	\bar{X}	SD	Rmks
11.	Digital communication devices	20	20	30	196	1.49	0.92	Low Extent
12.	Desktops	9	50	20	187	1.55	0.91	Low Extent
13.	Internet access	0	0	254	12	1.95	0.21	Low Extent
14.	Software applications	2	3	201	60	1.80	0.48	Low Extent
15.	Laptops	29	31	200	6	2.31	0.69	Low Extent
16.	Computer storage devices	3	6	198	59	1.82	0.50	Low Extent
17.	Uninterrupted power supply	0	0	18	248	1.07	0.25	Low Extent
18.	Servers	0	10	208	48	1.86	0.45	Low Extent
	Cluster Summary	-	-	-	-	1.73	0.44	Low Extent

Note: \bar{X} = Mean; SD = Standard Deviation; N = No of Respondents; N = 266.

From the result in Table 3 above, it was revealed that

the mean values of the respondents on the eight (8) items ranged from 1.07 to 2.31 which are all less than the cut-off point value of 2.50 on 4-point rating

scale. This indicates that the digital technologies are to a “Low Extent” available among polytechnics employees in Nasarawa State. The overall cluster mean value of 1.73 was less than 2.50 cut-off point, indicating that availability of digital technologies among polytechnics employees in Nasarawa State is generally low. The standard deviation values of the 8 items in the table ranged from 0.21 - 0.92 which

indicates that the responses of the respondents were close to one another and the mean.

Hypothesis Two

There is no significant difference on the mean rating of male and female employees on the extent of availability of digital technology in polytechnics in Nasarawa State.

The data for testing hypothesis two are presented in Table 4 below.

Table 4: Result of t-test Statistics of no Significant Difference in Mean Ratings of Male and Female Employees on Extent of Availability of Digital Technology in Polytechnics in Nasarawa State

Variables	N	\bar{X}	SD	DF	Std. Error	t-cal	t-tab	Level of sig.	Rmks
Male employees	146	1.69	0.45	264	0.037	1.69	1.96	0.05	NS
Female employees	120	1.78	0.43						

Note: NS = Not Significant at 0.05.

The data presented on the t-test statistics in Table 4 revealed that the t-calculated (t-cal) value of 1.69 was less than the t-table (t-tab) value of 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance and 264 degree of freedom. This showed that there was no significant ($p < 0.05$) difference in the mean ratings of the responses of male and female employees on the extent of availability of digital technology in polytechnics in Nasarawa State. Hence, the null hypothesis of no

significant ($p < 0.05$) difference in the mean ratings of the responses of male and female employees is accepted on hypothesis two.

Research Question three

What is the effect of digital skills on employee workplace operational efficiency in polytechnics in Nasarawa State?

The data for answering research question three are presented in Table 5 below.

Table 5: Mean Ratings of the Respondents on the Effect of Digital Skills on Employee Workplace Operational Efficiency in Polytechnics in Nasarawa State (n = 266)

SN	Effects of digital skills on efficiency	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	SD	Rmks
19.	It enhances operational efficiency	88	87	61	30	2.87	0.99	Agree
20.	Fosters innovation	90	106	42	28	2.96	0.95	Agree
21.	Contribute to the development of more skilled workforce	208	58	0	0	3.78	0.41	Agree
22.	Automate and streamline manual tasks	47	201	14	4	2.72	0.76	Agree
23.	Drives innovation and creativity	80	167	17	2	3.22	0.58	Agree

24.	Higher value activities	202	60	2	2	3.74	0.50	Agree
25.	It leads to strategic goals	86	115	64	1	3.08	0.75	Agree
Cluster Summary		-	-	-	-	3.20	0.65	Agree

Note: X = Mean; SD = Standard Deviation; N = No of Respondents; N = 266.

The result in Table 5 showed that the mean values of the respondents on the seven items ranged from 2.72 to 3.78 which are all greater than the cut-off point value of 2.50 on 4-point rating scale. This indicates that the respondents agreed that the seven identified items are effect of digital skills on employee workplace operational efficiency in polytechnics in Nasarawa State. The overall cluster mean value of 3.20 was greater than 2.50 cut-off point, indicating that the respondents agree that digital skills really have effects on employee

workplace operational efficiency in polytechnics in Nasarawa State. The standard deviation values of the seven items in the table ranged from 0.41 - 0.99 which implies that the responses of the respondents were close to one another and the mean.

Hypothesis Three

There is no significant difference in the mean rating of male and female employees on the effect of digital skills on employee in polytechnic work place operational efficiency in Nasarawa State.

The data for testing hypothesis three are presented in Table 6 below.

Table 6: Result of t-test Statistics of no Significant Difference in Mean Ratings of Male and Female Employees on the Effect of Digital Skills on Employee in Polytechnic Work Place Operational Efficiency in Nasarawa State

Variables	N	\bar{X}	SD	DF	Std. Error	t-cal	t-tab	Level of sig.	Rmks
Male employees	146	3.31	0.68						
				264	0.056	2.39	1.96	0.05	S*
Female employees	120	3.10	0.59						

Note: S* = Significant at 0.05.

The data presented on the t-test statistics in Table 6 showed that the t-calculated (t-cal) value of 2.39 was greater than the t-table (t-tab) value of 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance and 264 degree of freedom. This implied that there was significant (p<0.05) difference in the mean ratings of the responses of male and female employees on the effect of digital skills on employee in polytechnic work place operational efficiency in Nasarawa State. Consequently, the null hypothesis of no significant (p<0.05) difference in the mean ratings of the responses of male and female employees is rejected

on hypothesis three.

Discussion of Findings

The findings for research question one indicated that employees in Nasarawa State Polytechnics exhibit limited digital skills, especially in online navigation, digital communication, software application, computational procedures, management report generation, and email usage. These findings are consistent with earlier research, such as Oyebisi and Oyelami (2020), which linked low digital literacy among polytechnic employees to a lack of knowledge, motivation, and digital resources in addition to inadequate ICT training. Similar findings

were made by Chedi (2015), who discovered that polytechnic employees had poor digital competences, particularly when it came to using digital technologies to increase workplace productivity. The findings of this study on research question two showed that digital technologies such as digital communication devices, desktops, internet access, software applications, laptops, computer storage devices, uninterrupted power supply and servers are to a Low Extent available among polytechnics employees in Nasarawa State. This discovery aligns with previous research by Olofin and Aniele (2015) and Oyebisi and Oyelami (2020), which highlighted the inadequate availability of digital facilities as a major obstacle to digital literacy among non-teaching staff. The findings of this study as regards research question three identified the effect of digital skills on employee workplace operational efficiency to include enhancing operational efficiency, fostering innovation, contributing to the development of more skilled workforce, automating and streamline manual tasks, driving innovation and creativity, higher value activities and leading to strategic goals. Regarding the impact of digital skills on workplace efficiency, the study found that possessing digital skills enhances operational efficiency, fosters innovation, and contributes to a more skilled workforce. These findings are consistent with research by Okolocha et al (2020), Helsper and Reidorf (2016), and Adams (2022), which demonstrated that digital literacy and skills significantly improve workplace performance, reduce repetitive tasks, and boost motivation.

Conclusion

Leveraging digital skills in work places from literature has demonstrated considerable promise in improving employees' operational efficiency in service delivery. Despite the overwhelming potentials of digital skills and facilities, the level of adoption and competencies in Nigerian polytechnics

is still very low relative to other developed countries of the world. Moreover, leveraging digital skills is hindered by limited access to quality training programs, inadequate infrastructure, and resistance to technological change. As the digital revolution continues to transform the workplace, acquiring digital skills has become an urgent necessity. This study therefore further concluded that digital skills possessed by employees in Polytechnics in Nasarawa State are low which could be as a result of unavailability of the required digital technologies in the institutions.

Recommendations

From the above findings and conclusion, the study recommended that:

- To remain competitive and effective in the digital age, polytechnic management should prioritize the training and professional development of staff in digital technologies. This will enable employees to upskill and reskill, staying abreast of the latest digital trends and innovations, and ultimately enhancing the institution's overall performance and reputation.
- The government and management of Polytechnics should ensure adequate provision of required digital facilities to enhance effectiveness and operational efficiency of staff of Polytechnics at state and federal levels.
- There should be adequate provision of very stable electricity and internet connectivity in Polytechnics campuses for effective use of digital facilities that will guarantee operational efficiency of staff.

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